

MINDSITE

Empowering Adolescents to Sidestep Self-Diagnosis and its Social Relation

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1 INTRODUCTION

Constant access to the vast **information** available **online** regarding **mental health issues** influences **adolescents** to **self-diagnose**. The trend of self-diagnosis changes the way adolescents **perceive themselves and others**.

Furthermore, self-diagnosis action has an impact on **society**, one of which is in the form of **stigmatizing behavior**. Therefore, **treatment** is also needed to address this issue by increasing **education** about mental health to **shift stigmatizing beliefs** about people with **mental illness**.

2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE AND BENEFITS

Determine the correlation between self-diagnosis tendencies and stigmatizing behavior, as well as initiate MINDSITE as a solution offered to address the problem.

3 RESEARCH QUESTION

How is the relationship between individual identity construction related to self-diagnosis and the tendency towards stigmatization of mental health issues?

4 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

What is MINDSITE?

MINDSITE is an adoption of **website-based Mindfulness method** which contains Mindful Reading, mental health literacy based on DSM-5, Mindfulness videos and articles inviting socialization with people with mental disorders and consulting with professionals.

<https://sites.google.com/view/mindsite-therapy/beranda>

5 RESULT AND ANALYSIS

The tendency towards **self-diagnosis increases** when the **intensity of internet use to access mental health content** is also **high**, which is in line with previous studies which stated that self-diagnosis is significantly correlated with the intensity of internet use (Griffiths, 2011)

A **pilot project** was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of MINDSITE, which showed a **very high significance** value in the post-test treatment group (**p<0.001**), meaning that MINDSITE can be a **solution** to reduce the tendency of self-diagnosis, thus reduce stigmatizing behavior

Self-diagnosis and stigmatization have a **very strong positive** correlation ($r = 0.887$), indicating that as adolescents are more likely to self-diagnose, their tendency toward stigmatization also increases

Self-stigma most often occurs as **prejudice** (e.g., low self-esteem, low self-efficacy). Whereas **public stigma** most often occurs as **discrimination** (e.g., avoidance, withhold employment & help)

6 CONCLUSION

The tendency of adolescents to self-diagnose due to general mental health information available online has a very strong positive correlation with stigmatizing behavior, both self-stigma and public stigma. Therefore, MINDSITE is relevant to be offered as a solution to overcome the problem of self-diagnosis by increasing mental health literacy, so that it can reduce the tendency of stigmatization.

7 FUTURE WORK

- Further research can be conducted on more diverse respondents, such as adults and individuals with different socio-demographic backgrounds.
- This study can also be a reference for further research in providing similar treatment and its development related to the issues of self-diagnosis and stigmatization.

8 REFERENCES

- [1] Bippert, A. (2023). Hey, I Have That: Mental Health Self-Diagnosis in the age of TikTok.
- [2] Corrigan, P. W., & Watson. (2002). *Understanding the impact of stigma on people with mental illness*.
- [3] Goffman, E. (1963). *Stigma: Notes on the Management of Spoiled Identity*. Simon & Schuster.
- [4] Jorm, A. F. (2012). *Mental health literacy: Empowering the community to take action for better mental health*.
- [5] Kim, J., LaRose, R., & Peng, W. (2020). *Social media use and mental health: A systematic review*